

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63,1736 Max: 63,2632	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1270 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
	In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1195-1197	

DEFINITION Fill of round cut in "Room III"	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1218	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1272	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 60% sand 30% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	Compaction	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery R <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
			Color	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1218	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1272

OBSERVATIONS Monday (27-7) Fill baked hard on top, but loosened to become more typical of fill a few cm down. Excavated afternoon and Tuesday morning (28-7) before break. Excavated with trowel.

DESCRIPTION Position within sector: W wall of "Room III" (btwn the other 2 cuts)
Shape: semi-circle (uneven)

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): No slope
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Rocks, not much ceramic, almost no bones; no clusters or discernable patterns.
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): pretty even throughout
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

95cm

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

It's a semi-circular pit of unknown use.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CAK	on	28-7-10
Revised by	CHM	on	28.7.10
PDFd by	JJM	on	29.7.2010
Entered by		on	